

Human Resource Development in Bihar

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Abstract

Human resource is a basic concept of human development. The qualitative and quantitative aspects of human resource play a vital role in the progress of the society and the nation. HRD is concerned with affecting an increase in the productivity of man or with the formation of human capital. The development of human resource is a process which helps to improve the functional capabilities, to harness the potentialities of their self and the society. The state of Bihar retains a large number of poor people as human resource which is characterized by poverty, illiteracy, ill-health and malnutrition. The paper intends to diagnose the problems and prospects of Human Resource Development in Bihar.

Keywords

Functional, Harness, Malnutrition, Diagnose, Prospects etc.

Introduction

The qualitative and quantitative aspects of Human resource play a crucial role in the process of development of a region. The human resource, a dynamic phenomenon occupies the central position. A region bears an indelible imprint of the human resource in its totality. The level of development and spatial pattern of the region depends primarily on its human situation. Human resource is a key to the economic development of a region, because without human resources, nothing can be achieved. Human resources with its fullest level of skill development can strengthen the economic prosperity and overall development of an area.

Objective of study

The main objective of this study is to know the concept of HRD, its role in national reconstruction, its problems and to suggest solutions for development in the state of Bihar.

Review of Literature

A lot of literature is available on population and its various aspects. G.T. Trewartha has discussed in detail the various components of population. Prof. G.S. Gosal has written a book on 'Population Geography'. Prof. Jasbir Singh has done a lot on the population study of Haryana. R.C. Chandna has written a book on 'population Geography'. During the past decades, a number of scholars have written articles on population Geography which throw ample light on the subject.

Analysis

Human Resource Development : Conceptual Framework

Human Resource Development is concerned with affecting an increase in the productivity of man or with the formation of human capital. Human Development is being conceived as destination and human resource development is concerned as the means to achieve the same. Understandably, such fact of population, as literacy and education, employment, health and longevity assume significance in such studies concerning human resource development or human development. It includes such quantitative and qualitative aspects of population as number, growth rate, education,, skills, health and life expectancy of birth, social and political institutions, cultural values, honesty, work drive etc.

The development of human resource is nothing but a process, which helps to improve the functional capabilities for their inner present and future roles, to harness potentialities for their self and society. Lack of opportunity and motivation is the basic hindrance in human resource development and as a result, they remain only mob. Socio-economic disparities in Bihar furnish a very sensitive index of the quality in human life. The basic conditions necessary for human emancipation include equity in various fields, empowerment of the people, freedom of thought and expression and decolonisation of mind. In the absence of basis elements, no amount of wealth and comforts can provide the feelings of human fulfilment.

Indicators

After decades of planned development programmes, overall quality of human population has not improved in a perceptible manner. It is in the fields of literacy, nutrition level and freedom from epidemics. It is simply reflected in widespread growing the feeling of unfulfilment, discontent, alienation etc. In Bihar, human values have deteriorated fast and a deep erosion in human dignity has occurred. The indicators being employed presently to assess the level of human resource

development is not so sensitive and revealing. For instance, whereas literacy/education decidedly increase awareness and add to the skills of people, it also makes its own share in the burgeoning white-collar crime. Similarly, it contributes significantly to strengthen the circuit's exploitation and subjugation. Thus, being a double-edged tool, literacy and education indicators need to be carefully applied in the specific context of obtaining moral values of the people. The use of average employment fails to bring out the real situation in this regard. While making use of this indicator due attention needs to be accorded to the share of the aged people and children in the working population. It goes without saying that higher the proportion of these two groups of workers in the working population, the lower would be the quality of human resource development. If it is analyzed and assessed in terms of following conditions: equity, power, freedom and security, a meaningful and comprehensive view would result. Where these conditions are found in great measure for the people at large, there would be greater feeling of fulfilment, contentment, creativity and social solidarity etc and vice-versa. Though it would require a much greater investment in terms of time, data and efforts to analyse human resource development in this framework.

The conditions of equity, power, freedom and security can be interpreted under the following heads :

1. Socio-economic disparities
2. Empowering People
3. Freedom of thought and expression
4. Decolonisation

Result and Discussion

Literacy is that cultural attribute of population which is a reliable index of the socio-economic development of an area. Universal literacy and education are generally correlated with such trait of modern civilization as urbanization, industrialization, communication and commerce are indispensable to the advancement of nation in the present day world.

After bi-furcation of Bihar from Jharkhand, the remaining Bihar experienced several constraints. Bihar is completely devoid of mineral resources, forests, industries and power. Scarcity of these resources has put development process of Bihar at grinding halt. Bihar now possesses vast tract of Gangetic plain in the name of resources which experience frequent flood and drought.

Bihar retains a large population of the poor as human resource suffering from poverty and illiteracy. More than 40% population lives under poverty line and 35% illiterate in Bihar. Literacy rate of Bihar is very depressing and stands on the lower ladder in comparison to national figure. Though female literacy has increased but the male-female ratio is not up to the mark. The per capita income of Bihar is below 500 rupees. Population growth rate is very high due to high birth rate and low death rate. Urban and total density is soaring very high. Sex-ratio is remarkably low in many districts ranging between 850 to 1000. Table-1 shows the district-wise population size, growth rate, sex ratio, density, total literacy rate, male female literacy rate as per 2011 census. The highest literacy rate is found in the district of Patna and lowest in the district of Kishanganj. The highest sex ratio is in Siwan and lowest in Patna. The average state's sex ratio is 916 (2011) only.

Fig. 1.1

Table-1

Sl No	District	Area (Sq km)	Population		Population		Total	Population Growth Rate 2001-2011	Sex Ratio	Density	Literacy		Total
			Male	Female	Rural	Urban					Male	Female	
1.	Pashchim Champaran	5228	60271	431305	354177	393165	891576	29.29	906	750	68.16	46.79	58.06
2.	Purba Champaran	3698	268129	241812	469828	401343	5099371	29.43	901	1281	68.02	47.36	58.26
3.	Sheohar	349	346673	309573	628130	28116	656246	27.19	890	1881	63.72	47.25	56.00
4.	Sitamarhi	2294	180325	162032	323376	190498	3423574	27.62	899	1491	62.56	43.40	53.53
5.	Madhubani	3501	232931	215806	432584	161495	4487379	25.51	921	1279	72.53	48.30	60.90
6.	Supaul	2425	115523	107379	212358	105558	2229076	28.66	925	919	71.65	46.63	59.65
7.	Araria	2830	146333	134823	264292	168777	2811569	30.25	921	992	64.15	45.18	55.10
8.	Kishanganj	1884	866970	823430	152977	161123	1690400	30.43	946	898	65.56	47.98	57.04
9.	Purnia	3229	169937	156524	292169	343005	3264619	28.33	930	1014	61.09	43.19	52.49
10.	Katihar	3057	160043	147059	279707	273822	3071029	28.35	916	1004	60.99	45.37	53.56
11.	Madhepura	1788	104755	954203	1913301	88461	2001762	31.12	914	1116	63.82	42.75	53.78
12.	Saharsa	1687	997174	903487	174421	156540	1900661	26.02	906	1125	65.22	42.73	54.57
13.	Darbhanga	2279	205994	187743	355405	383328	3937385	19.47	910	1721	68.58	46.88	58.26
14.	Muzaffarpur	3172	252749	227356	432725	473437	4801062	28.14	898	1506	73.61	56.82	65.68
15.	Gopalgan	2033	126766	129434	239907	162805	2562012	19.02	1015	1258	78.38	56.03	67.04
16.	Siwan	2219	167509	165537	314754	182913	3330464	22.70	984	1495	82.77	60.35	71.59
17.	Saran	2641	202287	192904	359860	353202	3951862	21.64	949	1493	79.71	56.89	68.57
18.	Vaishali	2036	184453	165046	326194	233079	3495021	28.57	892	1717	77.07	59.10	68.56
19.	Samastipur	2904	223000	203156	411369	147797	4261566	25.53	909	1465	73.09	53.52	63.81
20.	Begusari	1918	156766	140288	240078	569823	2970541	26.44	894	1540	74.36	57.10	66.23
21.	Khagaria	1486	883486	783100	157927	87159	1666886	30.19	883	1115	68.51	52.16	60.87
22.	Bhagalpur	2569	161566	142210	243523	602532	3037766	25.36	879	1180	72.30	56.49	64.96
23.	Banka	3020	106714	967623	1963450	71313	2034763	26.48	907	672	60.12	69.76	49.40
24.	Munger	1419	729041	638724	987645	380120	1367765	20.21	879	958	80.06	65.53	73.30
25.	Lakhisarai	1228	526345	474567	857901	143011	1000912	24.77	900	815	73.98	54.89	64.95
26.	Sheikhpura	689	329743	306599	527340	109002	636342	21.09	929	926	76.14	54.93	65.96
27.	Nalanda	2355	149706	138059	241975	457894	2877653	21.39	921	1220	77.11	54.76	66.41
28.	Patna	3202	307851	275995	332875	251459	5838465	23.73	892	1803	80.28	63.72	72.47
29.	Bhojpur	2395	143038	129802	233857	389861	2728407	21.63	900	1136	84.08	60.20	72.79
30.	Buxar	1703	887977	818375	154185	164499	1706352	21.67	922	1003	82.78	59.84	71.77
31.	Kaimur (Bhabua)	3332	847006	779378	1560813	65571	1626384	27.50	919	488	81.49	59.56	71.01
32.	Rohtas	3881	154354	141632	253215	427765	2959918	20.11	914	763	85.29	64.95	75.59
33.	Aurangabad	3305	131868	122138	230319	236854	2540073	26.18	916	760	82.52	62.05	72.77
34.	Gaya	4976	226656	212485	380982	581601	4391418	26.43	932	880	76.02	55.90	66.35
35.	Nawada	2494	114468	107447	200356	215579	2219146	22.63	936	889	71.40	51.09	61.63
36.	Jamui	3098	916064	844341	161507	145333	1760405	25.85	921	567	73.77	49.44	62.16
37.	Jehanabad	931	585582	539731	990117	135196	1125313	21.46	918	1206	79.30	56.24	68.27
38.	Arwal	638	363497	337346	648994	51849	70083	19.23	927	1099	81.27	56.85	69.54
	Bihar State	9416	541853	496192	923414	117580	1038046	25.07	916	1102	71.20	51.50	61.80

Source : District Census Handbook, 2011

Conclusion

Though the Government is trying its best to spread literacy and education, but still there are a lot of pockets and villages where there is no school at primary level, In remote rural areas, there is lack of proper education environment. A

considerable number of boys and girls drop their education in the mid time due to poverty and economic reasons. Most of the children are engaged in different labour activities. Most of the schools lack basic infrastructural facilities like building, toilet, playground drinking water facilities, roads, electricity etc. Working culture is not satisfactory due to several factors like inadequate number of teachers, staff, lack of funds, Supervision and mismanagement, irresponsible conduct and behaviour of teachers are also responsible for deteriorating education system.

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